

Phytochemical and Proximate Composition of Aqueous leaf extract *Leptadenia hastata* (Decne)

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Abstract

Leptadenia hastata (Decne) is a climbing shrub which produces many flexible latexes that become woody at the bottom. The plant is used as nutritional as well as for medicinal purpose because of its health promoting properties. This study focused on the determination of phytochemical and proximate composition of aqueous leaf extract of *Leptadenia hastata* (Decne). Phytochemical and proximate composition were determined according to the methods of AOAC, 1990 and AOAC, 2010 respectively. phytochemical screening showed the presence of alkaloids, Saponins, Tannins, and Flavonoids. The result of the proximate composition indicated that crude fibre content was the highest ($27.00 \pm 0.03\%$), followed by the ash content (23.00 ± 0.006), Carbohydrate ($21.84 \pm 0.68\%$), Crude Protein (13.92 ± 0.32), Crude lipid (7.53 ± 0.91), and a low moisture content (4.48 ± 0.60). From the Results obtained *L. hastata* leaves possesses a rich phytochemical and nutritional. Profile which can be utilised as pharmacological agents in the treatment of some diseases as well as meet the nutritional requirement of the body.

Keywords: Leaf extract, *Leptadenia hastata*, Phytochemical, Proximate composition

1.0 Introduction

In Nigeria, and West African regions, herbal medicine practitioners have made several claims regarding the diverse phytochemical and nutritional properties of several plant species which usually forms the basis for their usage [1]. Also, vegetables are known to be an important aspect of the human diet because of their rich nutritional profile [2] *Leptadenia hastata* (Decne), also referred to as Yadiya in Hausa is evenly distributed across tropical Africa: Spanning Mauritania and Senegal eastwards to Cameroon and Ethiopia. Jansen in his report in 2004 stated that “this plant is now gaining wide spread awareness across Nigeria especially in the north central zone” [2]. *L. hastata* leaves are more abundant and fresher during rainy season [3]. In Nigeria is commonly consumed in Nigeria by the Hausa speaking communities where it is used as

spices and sauce [4]. Many considered this plant as a famine food hence, when there is food scarcity and there is no other alternative, the next action is to resort to consumption of *L. hastata* leaves. However, this is not always the case because many low-income earners eat this plant as a normal meal even in absence of famine [5]. In different ecological zones of Nigeria, especially in the northern axis, leaves, young shoots and flowers of *L. hastata* are eaten as cooked vegetable and in some instances as soup [6]. Studies have shown the potential *L. hastata* for various traditional purposes such as, hypertension, skin diseases, catarrh, wound healing, prostate problems and as an aphrodisiac. *L. hastata* is reported to contain alkaloids, saponins phenolic glycosides, flavonoids, Tannins, and Triterpenes [7]. In Nigeria is commonly consumed in Nigeria by the Hausa speaking communities where it is used as spices and sauce [8]. It is globally used

traditionally in the management and treatment of many known diseases [5]. *L. hastata* leaves are more abundant and fresher during rainy season [3]. The present study therefore is aimed at evaluating the phytochemical and proximate composition of aqueous leaf extract of *L. hastata*

2.0 Materials and Methods

2.1 Sample Collection

L. hastata leaves were plucked from, the Botanical Garden of Waziri Umaru Federal polytechnic and identified at the biology unit of the Department. The leaves were dried for fourteen (14) days at room temperature under shed. The dried leaves were grounded using pestle and mortar and then sieved. The sieved samples were kept in an air tight polythene bag for protection against moisture. The bag containing the sieved samples was kept in a dark and cool place and later taken for analysis at the biochemistry laboratory of Department of science technology, Waziri Umaru Federal Polytechnic, Birnin Kebbi, Kebbi State, Nigeria.

2.2 Extract Preparation

A 50g sample of the extract was extracted with 500 ml of distilled water for 48 hours. The mixture was decanted and filtered using sterile whatman filter paper No1. The filtrate measured up to 450 ml and evaporated to dryness using a freeze drier to obtain a 20% yield. The crude extract was later subjected to Bioassay analysis.

2.3 Phytochemical Analysis

Phytochemical analysis was determined using standard procedures [8]

2.4 Proximate Analysis

Proximate composition was determined using the method of analysis described by [9].

2.4.1 Determination of Moisture Content

Determination of the moisture content was done by adopting method of [9] with some slight modifications. A 2g sample of the extract was weighed (W1) into pre-weighed crucible (W0) and placed in an oven at 105°C for 45 minutes. The crucible was then removed and cooled in a desiccator after which it was then weighed. This process was repeated until a constant weighed

(W2) was achieved. The percentage moisture content was determined by the following equation;

$$\% \text{ moisture} = \frac{W_1 - W_2}{W_2 - W_0} \times 100$$

Where: W₀ = weight of the empty crucible (g)

W₁ = weight of fresh sample + crucible (g)

W₂ = weight of dried sample + crucible (g)

2.4.2 Ash content

The ash content was determined using the dry ashing method. The weight of the crucible was taken on a weighing balance 4g of the sample was weighed in a crucible of known weight using a weighing balance. The sample was ashed in the muffle furnace at a temperature of 600°C for 6h. The ash obtained was transferred into a desiccator and cooled. The weight of crucible + ash was obtained using a weighing balance and % ash content was calculated [9].

2.4.3 Crude protein content

A Foss digester was used to digest the sample and a Kjeltic distiller (Foss) was used to extract ammonia. 1g of sample was transferred into a digestion tube. 12ml of concentrated H₂SO₄, 7g of potassium sulphate, and 0.08g of copper sulphate were weighed and transferred into the digestion tube. The mixture in the digestion tube was digested at 400°C. The digest was allowed to cool and 75ml of water was added to dilute the acid. 60 ml of the alkaline solution was added to the sample in a digestion tube (sodium thiosulphate, sodium hydroxide, and water). The sample was then distilled in a Kjeltic distiller using 25ml of 4% boric acid to trap ammonia which was titrated against HCl until a pink colour was obtained [9].

Moles of HCl = Moles of NH₃ = Moles of nitrogen in the sample. A blank (sucrose) was used also to titrate substrate reagent nitrogen from the sample. Where 14.01 is the atomic weight of nitrogen and 6.25 is the factor used to convert percent nitrogen to crude protein.

2.4.4 Crude fat content

The crude fat content was determined by the method of [9]. Using Soxhlet extraction method. Soxhlet auto extraction machine was used to extract the total lipid content. 3g of sample was weighed in cellulose thimbles 60ml of hexane was added into the cups. Hexane was used to extract the oil from the sample. The thimbles and the crucible were placed in the right positions in a

soxhlet extraction unit. Complete extraction takes about 1hrs and the process includes heating at 20°C. The extracted oil in the cups was further dried in an oven for 30 min at a temperature of 105°C to ensure complete evaporation of hexane. Crucible containing extracted oils was allowed to cool in a desiccator and weighed [9].

2.4.5 Crude fibre content

The crude fibre was analyzed using the method described by [10]. A 2g sample of the extract was weighed in a beaker and noted as w_1 . 100 ml of a mixture of trichloroacetic acid, nitric acid, and Ash (%) = Crude protein (%) = Fat (%) = $\times 100$ glacial acetic acid and water (20g of trichloro acetic acid, 50ml nitric acid, 450ml glacial acetic acid, and 500 ml water) mixture was placed on a reflux condenser and allowed to reflux for 1 h. After which the sample was filtered into a round bottom flask through a filter paper placed on a funnel. The residue obtained on the filter paper was transferred into a crucible. The crucible was transferred into an oven and allowed to dry for 24 hours at a temperature of 110°C. After 24 h, the crucible was allowed to cool in a desiccator and the weight of extract + crucible. The sample was incinerated in a muffle furnace for 6h and then cooled in a desiccator.

$$\text{Crude fibre (\%)} = \frac{w_2 - w_3}{w_1} \times 100$$

2.4.6 Total carbohydrate

Total carbohydrate was obtained by difference having estimated all other fractions: Available carbohydrate (%) = $100 - (\% \text{ moisture} + \% \text{ ash} + \% \text{ protein} + \% \text{ lipids} + \% \text{ fibre})$ [9].

2.5 Statistical analysis

The analysis was performed in triplicates. The mean values and standard deviation were calculated using SPPSS package 16

3.0 Results

The results of the phytochemical screening are shown in Table 1. Phytochemical screening showed the presence of higher amounts of Tannins and flavonoids while alkaloids and Saponins were present in moderate amount.

Table 1: Qualitative Phytochemical Constituent of aqueous leaves extract of *L. hastata*

S/N	Phytochemical Parameters	Concentration
1.	Alkaloids	++
2.	Saponins	++
3.	Tannins	+++
4.	Flavonoids	+++
5.	Cardiac glycosides	-
6.	Phenols	-

Keys =: +++ =Highly present, ++ =Moderately present, + =Slightly present, - =Not detected

The result of the proximate composition indicated that crude fibre content was the highest ($27.00 \pm 0.03\text{g\%}$), followed by the ash content (23.00 ± 0.006), Carbohydrate ($21.84 \pm 0.68\text{g\%}$), Crude Protein (13.92 ± 0.32), Crude lipid (7.53 ± 0.91), and a low moisture content as shown in table 2

Table 2: Proximate composition of aqueous leaf extract of *L. hastata*

S/N	Parameters	Concentration (%)
1.	Ash	23.00 ± 19.15
2.	Moisture	4.48 ± 0.600
3.	Crude Protein	13.92 ± 0.32
4.	Crude Lipid	7.53 ± 0.91
5.	Crude Fibre	27.00 ± 3.00
7.	Carbohydrate	21.84 ± 0.68

Values are expressed as mean \pm standard deviation of individually analysed triplicate.

4.0 Discussion

The phytochemical screening results obtained revealed the presence of alkaloids, saponins tannins, and flavonoids in *Leptadenia hastata* leaves extract. However, cardiac glycosides and phenols were not detected.

Alkaloids are considered as basic naturally occurring organic compound that contains at least anitrogen atom, alkaloids play a very significant role in organisms metabolic and functional activities, alkaloids are considered as metabolic product in plants, animals and microorganisms as reported [11]. In this present study alkaloid was found to be present in *L. hastata* aqueous leaf extract in moderate amount this tally with the work of [12].

Saponins have been reported to have antioxidant, antiinflammatory, antiphotosynthetic, immune stimulants, and antineurode generative property. In the present study, saponins was present in moderate amount which is in with the study of [12], who reported the presence of slight amount of saponins in comparative study of *L. hastata* and *Vitex doniana*.

Tannins are also exceptional group of water-soluble metabolites of relatively high molecular weight, and having the ability to complex with carbohydrate Proteins as reported by [13]. In this present study, Tannin was present in moderate amount, this work is similar to work [12] and [15]. Who reported the presence of tannin in ethanolic extract of *L. hastata* leaves.

Flavonoids are known as Lipophenolic compounds that are abundant in nature and can be categorized according to their structure. Flavonoids and Anthocyanodines, Isoflavones, Catechins, Flavounols Chalcones, and Flavannones [14]. Flavonoids have been recorded to possess many useful effects on human health, they have also been shown to have several biological properties which include anti-inflammatory activity, enzyme inhibition, antimicrobial activity oestrogenic activity antioxidant and free radical scavenging activity [11]. In the present study flavonoids was present in the aqueous leaf extraction of *L. hastata* leaves in high amounts, this correlates with the work of [15], who reported a high flavonoid content in the ethanolic leave extract of *L. hastata*

The proximate analysis result of aqueous leaf extract of *L. hastata* showed a low moisture content of (4.48 ± 0.60) which is the least of all the parameters. This aligns with the report by [15], who reported a low moisture content in *L. hastata* leave powder (7.63%). This is in contrast with other similar vegetable plants as reported by [16], such as *Telfairia occidentalis* (12.05%), *Amaranthus hybridus* (10.00%) and *Vernonia amygdalina* (10.02%) and (7.00%) for *Moringa*

oleifera as reported by [14]. The low moisture content allows for a longer shelf life of *L. hastata* leaf extract [14].

Ash content is used as an indicator of mineral content in plants. In this study *L. hastata* leaf extract showed a high amount of ash (23.00%). Minerals are essential for proper functioning of tissues and act as second messengers in some biochemical reaction mechanism [17]. This result corroborates with the work of [15] who earlier reported high ash content fashionable crude powder of *L. hastata*. (14.1) and (13.80) for *Amaranthus hybridus* as reported by [18].

The lipid content of *L. hastata* in this present study was $(7.53 \pm 0.91\%)$. Lipids are universally stored forms of energy in living organisms. They the major structural elements of biological membranes [19]. This work is in contrast to the work of [15], who reported a low lipid content in the leaves of *L. hastata*, $(2.7 \pm 0.06\%)$.

The crude fiber was high (27.00 ± 3.00) when compared with the work of [15], who reported the value for crude fibre as (7.50 ± 0.05) . this result also tallies with the report of [16] who reported higher crude fibre content of leafy vegetables such as *Hibiscus sabderiffa* (12.04), *Vernonia amygdalina* (12.08), *Telfaira occidental* (11.05) as well as *Moringa oleifera* (20.00 ± 0.03) [14].

The carbohydrate content (2.84 ± 0.68) was lower than (47.13 ± 0.70) which was reported by [15]. [14] also reported a higher carbohydrate content for *Moringa olifera* leaves (23.60 ± 0.20) . Proteins serves as enzymatic catalyts, mediate cell responses, and control cell growth and differentiation [20]. Crude protein (13.92 ± 0.32) was lower when compared with the report by [15], (20.85 ± 0.07) and lower than that of *Amaranthus hybridus* (17.92) [18].

5.0 Conclusion

From this research, it could be established that *L. hastata* leaf extract boasts of a wide array of phytoconstituents which are of medicinal and pharmacological importance. More so, the plant extract can be used as a good source of nutrients because of its high proximate content.

6.0 References

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